

Increasing efficacy of urea in wetland rice cultivation

Syed Nazeer Peeran and S. Natanasabapathy, Soil Science Section, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur 602025, Chingleput Dist., Tamil Nadu, India

Field trials in sandy loam soils for two seasons investigated the efficacy of urea for wetland rice. The experiments were in strip-plot design with 3 main treatments (nitrogen levels, 0, 75, 150 kg/ha)

and 6 subtreatments of mode of urea application.

The efficacy of placement of urea by applicator or through paper ball was pronounced when urea was applied in two doses: 1/2 as placement on the 15th day and 1/2 as topdressing on the 35th day after planting (see table). Between the two methods of placement, the paper ball was more efficacious.

An important feature of urea place-

ment was the saving of about 50% of the fertilizer compared to a conventional method of application (1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressing). The yield of 4.0 to 4.2 t/ha obtained in 1980 navarai with the application of 150 kg N/ha by the conventional method was equal to the yield obtained with application of 75 kg N/ha as 1/2 placement on the 15th day + 1/2 as topdressing on the 35th day after planting. ■

Effect of mode of nitrogen application on rice grain yield. PES, Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India, 1979-80.

Mode of application and N levels ^a	Grain yield (t/ha) for 1979 samba (IR20)				Increase (%) over control	Grain yield (t/ha) for 1980 navarai (TKM9)				Increase (%) over control
	0 N	75 kg N	150 kg N	Mean		0 N	75 kg N	150 kg N	Mean	
T1 = all basal	1.6	2.1	2.2	2.0	100	2.1	3.2	4.0	3.1	100
T2 = 1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressed	1.5	2.0	2.4	2.0	100	2.0	3.5	4.2	3.2	103
T3 = all by applicator 15 DP	1.6	2.2	2.5	2.1	105	2.0	3.5	4.4	3.3	106
T4 = all by paper ball 15 DP	1.6	2.3	2.7	2.2	110	2.0	3.8	4.5	3.4	110
T5 = 1/2 by applicator 15 DP + 1/2 broadcast 35 DP	1.5	2.5	2.8	2.3	115	2.1	3.9	4.6	3.5	113
T6 = 1/2 by paper ball 15 DP + 1/2 broadcast 35 DP	1.6	2.7	2.9	2.4	120	2.2	4.2	4.8	3.1	119
Mean	1.5	2.3	2.6			2.1	3.7	4.4		
% over control	100	153	173			100	176	210		
		<i>F-test</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>CD</i>		<i>F-test</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>CD</i>		
Main treatment (levels of N)		S**	0.092	0.319		S**	0.034	0.118		
Subtreatment (mode of N application)		S*	0.083	0.250		S**	0.082	0.246		
<i>Interactions:</i>										
a) Sub at main		NS	0.124	—		NS	0.148	—		
b) Main at sub		NS	0.196	—		NS	0.201	—		

^a DP = days after planting.

Influence of soil water treatments on nutrient availability in soil and yield of dryland rice

R. V. Ghugare, K. R. Sonar, and G. K. Zende, Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science Department, Mahatma Phule Agricultural University (MPAU), Rahuri 413722, Maharashtra, India

A field experiment on a calcareous Vertisol (pH 8.6, CaCO₃ equivalent 9.8%, and organic carbon 0.68%) at MPAU in the 1978 rainy season investigated the effect of soil water treatments on the availability of nutrients in soil and on rice yield. For 15 days before rice was sown the following

soil water treatments were given: dry (no irrigation), saturation (about 6 cm irrigation on alternate days), and submergence (2 irrigations daily). Two rice varieties were compared: Karjat 184 (semidwarf, wetland) and Tuljapur 1 (tall, dryland). Soil moisture conditions were maintained at about yield capacity (dryland conditions) throughout crop growth. Changes in nutrient availability as a result of soil water treatments 5 days before sowing were studied and yields of rice grain and straw were recorded.

The available nitrogen, phosphorus, iron, and manganese supply in the soil (see table) increased with soil-water treatments 15 days before sowing. The availability of those nutrients was

significantly higher in the presowing soil-submergence treatment compared with the soil saturation and control treatments. This increase in nutrient availability might be due to moderately reducing soil conditions as a result of presowing soil submergence (the Eh value decreased from 501 to 362 mV and the pH decreased from 8.6 to 8.0).

Yields of rice grain and straw were significantly higher in the presowing soil water treatments. Yields of the soil submergence treatment 15 days before sowing were significantly higher than those of the control and the soil-saturation treatments. That could be because of the higher supply of nitrogen phosphorus, iron, and manganese in soil